

Role of Virechana in the Management of Vipadika - A Case Study

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Abstract:- All skin diseases in Ayurveda have been considered under the headings of kushta. Vipadika is one of the types of the Kshudrakushtha which involves Vata-Kapha dosha predominantly as stated by Acharya Charaka. It is characterized by Sphutanam (fissures) either in palms or soles or in both with Theevra vedana (severe pain). Looking from the modern point of view it can be correlated with Palmoplantar psoriasis. In the present case, A 30 years old male patient suffering from cracks in the palm, dryness, and intermittent itching for 2 years which increased from the last 6 months was treated with shodhan (virechana karma) and shaman chikitsa showed a significant result. Shodhana helps remove the root cause of the disease and prevent a recurrence.

Keywords:- Kushta, Vipadika, Palmar plantar psoriasis, Virechana, Shamana.

I. INTRODUCTION

The patient's quality of life is negatively impacted by psoriasis, a chronic, unpredictable, and immune-mediated condition. Due to its direct interference with daily activities, palmoplantar psoriasis might exacerbate this detrimental effect. Palmo-plantar psoriasis reduces considerable functional and social disability and makes up 2-4% of all instances of psoriasis.¹ Psoriasis prevalence ranges from 0.44 to 2.8% in India.² It is twice more common in males compared to females³. Palmo-plantar psoriasis is a variant of psoriasis resistant to many forms of treatment⁴.

All skin conditions have been classified under the kushta roga in Ayurveda.⁵

A. Vipadika –

One of the varieties of Kshudrakushtha (a dermatological condition) is vipadika. It is categorized as a Kshudrakushtha condition with VataKaphadosha involvement⁶ and According to Acharya Charak⁷, it is distinguished by Pani-Padasphutan (fissure in the palms and soles) and Tivravedana (extreme agony).

Acharya Vagbhat has stated the same as described by Acharya Charaka but mentioned one feature of red patches over palm and sole.

B. Palmo - plantar psoriasis

Vipadika can be correlated with Palmoplantar psoriasis which is a long-lasting autoimmune disease characterized by red, itchy, scaly patches of the palms and soles, there are multiple painful fissures and bleeding also. Palmar plantar psoriasis is caused by a combination of genetic and environmental factors. The most common genetic factor associated with palmar plantar psoriasis includes the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) On physical exam, thick hyperkeratosis plaques, sterile pustules, or a mixture of morphologies may be seen in palmar plantar psoriasis. Hyperkeratosis plaques are the most common subtype. Symmetrically distributed lesions are common, as well as erythema, fissuring, and scaling.⁸

Skin conditions have a high recurrence rate even with long-term treatment, therefore shodhana chikitsa i. e. virechana, which aids in removing the vitiated doshas from the body to prevent the recurrence of the disease, was chosen in this case. Shaman chikitsa was also chosen for this case and shaman chikitsa was also selected for this case.

II. CASE REPORT

A 30-year-old male patient visited CSMSS Ayurveda College, kanchanwadi Aurangabad Panchakarma OPD presented with c/o of fissures in the palm region, with pruritus which increases during cold and dry atmosphere and also having itching at night time, History of all above complaints in the last 2 years increased in the last 6 months.

➤ Past History-

Patient took allopathy treatment, and also advertisement related ointments. He also took topical steroids for local applications since one and half year but was not getting permanent relief because of recurrence of the disease. so, he came for further advance treatment in ayurveda.

➤ Personal history

Appetite: Decreased

Bowel: 1/ 2-3 days vibandha (Constipation)

Micturition: Regular

Sleep: Disturbed

Food: Mixed diet (Non veg intake more)

➤ *Vital data*

Pulse: 78 /Min

BP: 110/80 MmHg

Respiratory Rate: 16/Min

Weight: 74 kg

No pallor, icterus

➤ *Skin examination*

Site – Both Palms

Distribution- Asymmetrical (both Palms)

Dryness, itching and cracking of both the palms is seen (sphutana)

Surface –is rough and dry, margin- irregular

➤ *Nidana Panchaka*

Nidana - Ushna Aahar, Katu Ruksha Ahara, Vataja Ahara, Poorva Roopa – Nothing Specific 0.

Roopa - Cracking of palm (Sphutana), Tivratar vedana(pain), Kandu(itching)

Samprapti - Nidana Sevana =Vata Kapha Prakopa - Rasa Rakta Dhatu Dushana - Sthana Samshraya in Pani- Rushata of Pani, Sphutana of Pani- Teevra Vedana - Vipadika

Upashaya - Cracking and pain subsides on application of Shatadhauta Ghruta

Diagnosis: vipadika (palmo-plantarpsoriasis)

Table No. 1- Diagnosis

Sr.No.	Signs and Symptoms	Present/Absent
1	Pani sphutanam(fissure)	Present
2	Tivratar vedana(pain)	Present
3	Kandu(itching)	Present
4	Vibandha (Constipation)	Present
5	Disturbed Sleep	Present

Table No. 2- Treatment given-

Procedure	Medication	dose	Duration
Deepan and pachan	Panchakola churna	5 grams	Twice a day
Snehapan	Panchatikta ghruta	Day 1-30ml Day 2-60 ml Day 3-90 ml Day 4-120 ml Day 5-130ml	5 days samyak Snigdha lakshana observed
Sarvanga Abhyanga and Swedana	Nimba tail Nadi Swedana	Day 6,7,8 10 to 15 mins	3 days
Pradhan Karma i.e., Virechana Karma	Manibhadra Guda Total no of Vegas: 8	Day 9	1 Day
Samsarjana Krama	Rice gruel + green gram gruel i.e., peya, vilepi, yusha (akruta & kruta)	Day 9th only at night time. Day 10,11,12	3 days

Table 3: Follow up medication

Medicines	Dose	Days
Arogyavardhini vati	2 BD	10 Days
Panchatikta ghana vati	2 BD	10 Days
Gandhak Druti	External application	10 Days

➤ *Observation-*

Table no. 4 – Clinical features: Before & after treatment

Sr. no.	Clinical features	Before treatment	After treatment
1	Fissure	++	No fissure
2	Dryness of palm skin	+++	+
3	Itching	++	No itching

Fig 1:- Clinical features: Before & after treatment

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the first medication the symptoms like cracking of both palms, and itching, reduced. The patient was advised to follow up on medicine and for avoiding fried food items, junk food, curd, non-vegetarian diet, seafood, and milk products.

➤ *Deepana pachana*

• *Panchakola churna*

This Churna contain Pippali (Piper longum), Pippali moola (root of Piper longum), Chavya (Piper chaba), Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica), Nagara (Zingiber officinale)⁹. This combination corrects Agni Dushti, is an appetizer, carminative, and digestive.

Prior to the administration of snehapana, the body should have nirama state which is achieved by pachana & agni vridhhi achieved by deepana. These drugs which are digestives & carminatives stimulate enzymatic secretions, Hcl secretions, pancreatic & bile secretions, thereby proper assimilation of sneha can occur.

➤ *Snehapana*

• *Panchatikta Ghruta*¹⁰

It has 6 ingredients namely – Goghrita, Nimba, Guduchi, Vasa, Patola, Kantakari and all of them except ghruta have got tikta rasa, majority are having laghu, ruksha guna and kapha pittahara, rakta prasadana property.

➤ *Abhyanga*:

Nimba taila¹¹ Nimba twak is having Laghu, Ruksha guna, is Kaphapittahara and having kushtaghna property. It is processed in tila taila which is twachya.

➤ *Virechana*:

Manibhadra guda¹² It has 5 ingredients namely Vidanga, Haritaki, Amalaki, Trivrit, Guda and almost all are having Laghu, Ruksha guna, Ushna veerya, Tridoshaghna property. It has Trivrit as the main ingredient which is the best drug among all the purgatives and has less complication. As there is no addition of any drastic purgative, this is not going to hamper the strength of person considerably. It also has vidanga which is krimighna and guda as the base which is having raktashodhana property.

The process of Virechana by its action clears the micro channels of all over the body and enhances the absorption by the intestine and each and every tissue of the body which is helpful in providing benefits of further therapies.

IV. CONCLUSION

This case study showed that Ayurvedic management Virechana as Shodhana therapy and Shamana Aushadhi's appear to be highly helpful for the treatment of skin conditions similar to Vipadika. From the above case, it can be said that Palmo-plantar psoriasis can be successfully managed through Ayurvedic line of treatment.

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